

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B134
Date: 26th Sep 2005
Take Off: 10:22:52
Landing: 15:12:18
Flight Time: 4h49m26

Campaign: AMPEP
Operating Area: Bristol Channel, S & E coast to Teesside

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Graham Morgan	BAE Systems
2	Co-pilot	Alan Foster	Directflight
3	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist	Eiko Nemitz	CEH
5	Flight Manager	Maureen Smith	FAAM
6	Core Chemistry / CCM2	Doug Anderson	FAAM
7	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office
8	Filters	Stuart Heath	FAAM
9	CCN / CCM2	Jamie Trembath	FAAM
10	AMS	James Allan	University of Manchester
11	Bag Filler 1	Alan MacDonald	CEH
12	Bag Filler 2	Daniela Famulari	CEH
13	NOxy	Dave Stewart	UEA
14	PTrMS	Anne Hulse	UEA
15	WAS	Debbie O'Sullivan	UEA
16			
17			
18			
19			
20			

Flight Track:

B134 Track 26-SEP-05

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b134
 Date: 26/09/05
 Project: AMPEP
 Location: S & E coasts to Newcastle

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
085428		Start posn	0.28 kft	126	52'04.36N, 0'37.48W
093035		INU	0.28 kft	126	To Nsvigate
102252		T/O	0.72 kft	232	Cranfield
102850		NOxy	10.0 kft	266	Cal Run
103009		ASPs	10.0 kft	247	Open
103651		Videos	10.0 kft	255	Start FFC & DFC
105527		Descend	9.9 kft	227	Bristol Channel
110225	111833	Run 1.1	0.94 - 0.97 kft	229	1k' on 1017mB WP48
111609		Turn	0.93 kft	205	at WP37
112112	112642	Run 2	5.0 kft	141	
112759	112905	Run 3	6.0 kft	141	
112926	113300	Profile 1	6.0 - 1.9 kft	146	
113322	113444	Run 4	1.9 kft	143	2000'
113807	114322	Profile 2	5.0 - 0.36 kft	092	Down to 500' 1016mB
114322	114424	Run 5	0.36 - 0.33 kft	092	500'
114441	114501	Profile 2	0.20 - 0.09 kft	089	500' - 250'
114501	114601	Run 6	0.09 - 0.10 kft	090	250', 1019mB
114643	135520	Run 7.1	0.34 - 0.83 kft	100	500'
114846		WP 45	0.32 kft	095	
120205		WP 44	0.36 kft	068	
121627		WP 43	0.42 kft	086	1017mB
121701		Videos	0.36 kft	057	Change tapes
122714		WP 42	0.38 kft	055	
123950		WP 41	0.41 kft	003	1016mB
125154		WP 40	0.42 kft	329	1016mB
130050		WP 87	0.49 kft	286	
131246		QNH	0.53 kft	324	1013mB
132151		WP 80	0.60 kft	315	
132352		QNH	0.55 kft	316	1012mB
132439		QNH	0.58 kft	315	1011mB
133553		QNH	0.63 kft	313	1009mB
133557		WP 79	0.67 kft	318	
134048		QNH	0.67 kft	332	1008mB
134219		WP 78	0.69 kft	328	
134312		QNH	0.72 kft	351	1007mB
134823		QNH	0.74 kft	351	1006mB
134959		Turn	0.73 kft	312	Past Farne Islands
135110		QNH	0.79 kft	305	1005mB
135748	135849	Run 8	0.51 - 0.52 kft	129	250'
135822		Videos	0.53 kft	128	Change tapes
135849	140042	Profile 3	0.52 - 1.2 kft	130	250' - 1k'
140043	140142	Run 9	1.2 kft	140	1k'
140143	140355	Profile 3	1.2 - 2.3 kft	130	1k' - 2k'
140355	140504	Run 10	2.3 kft	155	2k'
140512	140932	Profile 3	2.3 - 6.2 kft	170	6k'
140944	141729	Run 11	6.3 - 6.2 kft	173	
142025		WP 79	0.93 kft	144	
142041	144335	Run 12	0.68 - 0.51 kft	141	500'
142955		QNH	0.60 kft	148	1010mB
143713		WP 80	0.57 kft	153	1012mB
144723		NOxy	10.0 kft	191	Cal Run
150347		ASPs	10.0 kft	197	Close
151218		Land	0.34 kft	248	Cranfield
151657		Stop Posn	0.33 kft	309	52'04.36N, 0'37.48W

GEOSTROPHIC WIND SCALE
IN KNOTS FOR ISOBARS AT 4 MB INTERVALS
POLAR STEREOGRAPHIC PROJECTION

B134 Track 26-SEP-05

Sortie Brief: AMPEP

Flight Number : B134

Mission Scientist: Eiko Nemitz, CEH

Date : 26-September-2005

Outline schedule:

07:00 – Power to aircraft – warm-up
09:00 – Briefing
10:15 – Clear aircraft and security check
10:30 – Doors close
11:00 – Take off Cranfield
16:00 – Land Cranfield
16:30 – Debrief
18:00 – Power down

Location: A coastal transect of the South and East Coast of England

Sortie Aims: To measure the UK pollutant budget of a range of gases and aerosols leaving the UK in gentle SSW airflow over the UK. The objective, in addition to measuring the export fluxes of pollutants is to derive the chemical processing (gas/aerosol partitioning & oxidation state) of the air mass.

Sortie Summary: The budget measurements will be obtained by flying off the South and East coasts along a coastal transect beginning in the Bristol Channel to sample background air off the coast of Cornwall. The transect of the UK outflow begins along the English Channel heading East to Dover then North to the point where airflow off the land stops, which according to current forecasts is North Yorkshire. Vertical profiles (250 – 6000 ft) once upwind in the Bristol channel and downwind of the source region off the Northumberland coast on the Southbound leg will provide the vertical structure in concentration and meteorology. These should clearly extend into the free troposphere (Mission Scientist to verify from profiles of humidity, temperature and CO. These measurements will establish the upwind concentration, the concentration differential at the top of the boundary layer and the concentration in the outflow from the source region. Flight ceiling will be 10000ft. Cabin pressure will be maintained at 1200ft, to minimize expansion of the Tedlar bags.

Sortie Detail with approx timing

- a) Take off Cranfield 13:00 and climb to 10000 ft for transit east to operating area, towards waypoint 37 in the Bristol Channel; background filter run (sampling) & NO_x calibration. Descend to 1000 ft as soon as possible into Bristol Channel, initiated over land.
- b) T+35: Cross Devon/Cornwall at 5000 ft.
- c) T+45: Descending upwind profile down to define the boundary layer structure off the coast with 1 min sampling at each height (2000, 500, 250)
- d) T+60: Return to 1000 ft for sampling..
Start of filter run No 1. Start of continuous bag sampling (1 bag every min) continue all the way up the east coast. 30-minute filter pack runs from here (called by Mission Scientist)

- e) T+ 200 U-turn off the Northumberland coast into wind, ascending downwind profile (250, 500, 2000, 4000, 6000).
- f) T+ 300 Land Cranfield

Crew List:

1. Pilot 1 - ?
2. Pilot 2 - ?
3. CCM - ?
4. CCM2/CCN - Jamie Trembath
5. Core Chemistry - Doug Anderson
6. Cloud Physics - Martyn Pickering
7. Flight Manager - Maureen Smith
8. Mission Scientist - Eiko Nemitz
9. Bag Sampling 1 - Alan McDonald
10. Bag Sampling 2 - Daniela Famulari
11. Filters - Stuart Heath
12. AMS - ?
13. NOxy - ?
14. PTRMS - ?
15. WAS - ?

- Transit to Bristol Channel
- descend to point 37 50:55N 4:50W
- 48 50:50N 4:40W
- 46 50:01N 3:25W
- 45 50:01N 2:00W
- 44 50:40N 1:00W
- 43 50:40N 0:30E
- 42 51:05N !:30E
- 41 51:53N 1:47E
- 40 52:41N 1:47E
- 87 53:00N 1:00E
- 80 54:05N 0:05E
- 79 50:00N 1:10W
- 77 55:45N 1:30W
- 79 50:00N 1:10W
- 80 54:05N 0:05E
- 87 53:00N 1:00E
- Cranfield

Instrumentation strategies & issues:

Filter sampling: Filters will be taken throughout the flight. Filter pack 1 will contain a Teflon filter for trace metal analysis. Filter pack 2 will contain a Teflon prefilter (for major ion analysis), a nylon filter (for HNO₃ & HCl) and an acidified paper filter (for NH₃). Filters will be changed approximately every 30 minutes or when flight conditions change (as advised by the Mission Scientist). Filters are preloaded into cartridges, which need to be handled with gloves and stored in sealed bags immediately. Filter sampling will be suspended during vertical profiles and resumed when FL10 is re-attained. During breaks, filter packs will be isolated by switching off the pump (to minimise evaporation of volatile aerosol components). During initial transfer to the operating area, a set of filters should be loaded into the filter packs, without sampling, to provide a blank value.

AMS: The AMS will be operated continuously during the flight. Monitored masses will include m/z 16, 18, 28, 30, 43, 44, 46, 57 and 64. The inlet remains closed until airborne to minimize contamination during taxi take-off.

Core Chemistry: CO, SO₂, NO and NO₂ will be measured continuously during the flight. CO will be calibrated every 30 minutes at 1000ft.

Tedlar bags: Tedlar bags will be filled at a flow rate of 6 lpm, filling a bag over a duration of 30 s. Bags will be filled every 3 minutes upwind and every minute downwind of the source region and during each leveling out for a profile step. Bags should be filled to about 90% of their capacity to maximise sample volume. The cabin pressure will be tightly controlled. Bags from first part of flight can be stored in cargo hold for second part.

Aerosol & cloud physics: CN and PCASP are operated continuously.

Core meteorology & state: Are recorded as standard. Video recording of front facing and downfacing cameras.

TDL for CH₄ and CO₂: N/A

Quick-look data: pressure height, lat, long, temp, RH, CN, SO₂, NO, NO₂, O₃, CO, NO_{xy}(HNO₃)

Mission Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.134**

 Date **26/09/2005**

 Page **1** of **3**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
10:23	V/O	overcast sea		V/O	
		cloud base 2000ft			; cloud top 2800ft
		in addition			high level cloud
10:27		lower level cloud			broken shortly after V/O
10:34		some precip			from high level clouds
10:40		CPC shows low conc			for white and goes back up to ~7000 while AMS CPC sees few hundred
10:47		Way out complete			
		moving into area			with over strato cloud cover
10:55		end of filter height sea			
11:00		descending into Bristol Channel			
		top at 3400 to 2800 ft			
11:02	R1	@ 1000 ft			wind 11 kts @ 212° or 25 kts @ 209°
11:02	FPI	Rm start			
11:16		WP 37			17 kts @ 199°
11:18	R1	end of Rm @ WP 48			
		suspended FT Rm 1			Co gradient flat in BL
		cloud 2500 - 3600 ft			
11:20	R2	@ 5000 ft			broken cloud below; high cloud above
11:27:59	R3	@ 6000 ft			
	P1	cloud stops at channel coast.			
		6000 → 2000			
		some individual cloud at 2000			
11:33	R4	@ 2000 ft			
11:34	R4	@ 2000 ft			return to 5000 to fix AMS problem

brief: scatter signs

Mission Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.134**.....

 Date **26/09/2005**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
11:37					GPS problem fixed
11:38	P2	5000 → 500 ft			
		Scattered cloud alt			1600 - 1000 ft
11:42	R5	@ 500 ft			
	P3	500 → 250			
	R6	250 ft			
11:46	R7	500 ft			
11:49	FP2	run start			
11:50		spikes on NOx			→ ship plumes? (CN also)
11:54		Wind 13 m/s @ 220°			/ 26 knots @ 234°
12:03		ship plumes (high NO)			
		spike in CO			which is remarkably flat overall.
12:13		Wind 14 m/s @ 249°			N 23/25°
12:16		WP 43			
12:27		WP 42			
#	FP2	end of run			
12:28		ship plumes			(Dust fumes & cargo)
12:32		Wind 13 m/s / 218°			at 22/223°
12:32	FP3	start			
12:40		ship plumes!			
13:00		fix plume on shore			10 m/s @ 197° / 213/22
13:06	FP3	end			
	FP4	start			
13:21		Wind 11 m/s @ 200°			/ 26 @ 205°
13:35		WP 79			
13:44		CEMENT WORKS (?)			plume

Mission Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.134**

 Date 26/09/2005

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
13:52					Wind Rays @ 190° / 35 / 192°
13:55	R7	end of run			
					end of run 4
13:58	R8	@ 250 ft			
13:59	P3	250 → 1000			
14:00	R9	1000 ft			
14:04	R10	2000 ft			
14:05	P3c	2000 - 6000 ft			
14:17	R10	end of run @ 6000 ft.			
14:20		WP 79			
14:20	FTS	start of run			
					a white layer, but horizon visible
					high level cloud; individual small clouds @ 1500 ft
14:33		spots of rain		17 kts @ 203°	26 km @ 199°
14:37		WP 80		@ 500 ft	
14:43	R12	end of run			to climb to FL100
					to clouds
					scattered cloud over land, no cloud / SE of Cranfield.
					cloud top 3700 ft; cloud base @ 2800 ft.
					+ overcast high level.
					PCH80 deemed questionable

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B134

Date: 27/09/05

Operator: MAP

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G.M.T.	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	DRS Time	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	
11:02:28											Start Run 1.1 @ 1000'
11:03:00	180	0.07	71		50						CH1 noise in PCASP
11:05:00	190	0.06			50						
11:07:00	110	0.07	72		40						
11:09:00	110	0.07			40						
11:11:00											Computer crash
11:13:00	140	0.07			60						
11:15:00	160	0.06			60						
11:17:00	150	0.06	73		60						
11:18:36											End of Run 1.1
11:21:10											Start Run 2 @ 5000'
11:22:00	50	0.06	92								
11:24:00	80	0.06									
11:26:00	60	0.06									
11:26:42											End of Run 2
11:28:02											Start Run 3 @ FL060
11:29:00	55	0.06									
11:29:10											End of Run 3
11:29:23	55	0.06									Start Profile 1 from FL060
11:30:24	50	0.06									FL050
11:31:15	90	0.07			15						4000'
11:32:03	90	0.07			20						3000'
11:33:02											End P1 start Run 4 @ 2000'
11:34:00	125	0.06			15						
11:34:44											End of Run 4
11:38:09	35	0.06	94								Start Profile 2 from FL050
11:39:16	50	0.06									FL040
11:40:05	120	0.06			10						FL030
11:41:09	200	0.06			50						FL020
11:42:12	180	0.06			90						FL010
11:43:24	200	0.06			70						End of P 2 Start Run 5 @ 500'
11:44:00	240	0.06			70						
11:44:31											End Run 5 restart P2
11:45:01	245	0.06			80						End of P2 start Run 6 @ 250'

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B134

Date: 27/09/05

Operator: MAP

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G.M.T.	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
DRS Time	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
11:46:00	220	0.06	94	60							
11:46:04											End of Run 6
11:46:45											Start Run 7.1 @ 500'
11:47:00	180	0.06		80							
11:49:00	190	0.06		70							
11:51:00	155	0.06	95	30							
11:53:00	210	0.06		40							
11:55:00	250	0.06		30							
11:57:00	360	0.06		50							
11:59:00	280	0.07		50							
12:01:00	160	0.06	96	40							
12:03:00	200	0.06		40							
12:05:00	170	0.06		30							
12:07:00	200	0.06		30							
12:09:00	240	0.06		30							
12:11:00	180	0.07	97	30							
12:13:00	200	0.07		20							
12:15:00	280	0.07		20							
12:17:00	310	0.07		20							
12:19:00	370	0.07		20							
12:21:00	510	0.07		15							
12:23:00	400	0.07		20							
12:25:00	525	0.08		15							
12:27:00	570	0.08	98	20							
12:29:00	590	0.07		20							
12:31:00	600	0.07		15							
12:33:00	420	0.07		10							
12:35:00	530	0.07		15							
12:37:00	360	0.07		15							
12:39:00	300	0.07		10							
12:41:00	280	0.07		10							
12:43:00	330	0.07		15							
12:45:00	440	0.07		10							

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B134

Date: 27/09/05

Operator: MAP

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
12:47:00	470	0.08	99	10							
12:49:00	520	0.08		15							
12:51:00	500	0.08		10							
12:53:00	380	0.08		10							
12:55:00	390	0.08		10							
12:57:00	320	0.08		10							
12:59:00	460	0.08		10							
13:01:00	340	0.08		20							
13:03:00	370	0.07		15							
13:05:00	290	0.07		20							
13:07:00	460	0.07		20							
13:09:00	470	0.08		20							
13:11:00	500	0.08		20							
13:13:00	630	0.08		20							
13:15:00	480	0.08	100	20							
13:17:00	360	0.08		15							
13:19:00	560	0.08		15							
13:21:00	630	0.08		15							
13:23:00	550	0.08		15							
13:25:00	620	0.08		20							
13:27:00	520	0.08		10							
13:29:00	630	0.08		10							
13:31:00	880	0.07		10							
13:33:00	780	0.07		10							
13:35:00	890	0.07		10							
13:37:00	900	0.07		15							
13:39:00	750	0.07	101	10							
13:41:00	815	0.08		10							
13:43:00	630	0.07		10							
13:45:00	600	0.07		10							
13:47:00	530	0.06		10							
13:49:00	530	0.07		20							
13:51:00	470	0.07		10							

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

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Date: 27/09/05

Operator: MAP

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G.M.T.	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	DRS Time	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	
13:53:00	395	0.07	101		10						
13:55:00	350	0.07			20						
13:55:20											End of Run 7.1
13:57:51											Start Run 8 @ 250'
13:58:00	320	0.07			15						
13:58:55	360	0.07			15						End Run 8 Start P3 from 250'
14:00:41											Hold P3 Start Run 9 @ 1000'
14:01:00	450	0.08			15						
14:01:47	455	0.08			10						End Run 9 continue P3
14:03:50	410	0.08			10						Hold P3 Start Run 10 @ 2000'
14:04:00	420	0.08			20						
14:05:07											End of Run 10 continue P3
14:06:25	250	0.08			10						FL030
14:07:29	135	0.07			5						FL040
14:08:21	100	0.07			5						FL050
14:09:17	75	0.08			5						End of Profile 3 @ FL060
14:09:52											Start Run 11 @ 6000'
14:10:00	90	0.07			5						
14:12:00	95	0.07			5						
14:14:00	60	0.06			2						
14:16:00	105	0.06			2						
14:17:30											End of Run 11
14:20:44											Start Run 12 @ 500'
14:21:00	660	0.08	102		10						
14:23:00	520	0.08			10						
14:25:00	580	0.08			10						
14:27:00	640	0.08			10						
14:29:00	680	0.08			15						
14:31:00	620	0.08			15						
14:33:00	600	0.07			30						
14:35:00	560	0.07			30						
14:37:00	530	0.07			20						
14:39:00	530	0.07			10						

B34

CCN LOG

CARDS? Paker 1/3

ALLEVIATOR GMT ON	OFF	HEIGHT	TEMP INLET	1	2	3	4	5	REMARKS
10:28:20	10:31:00	10000ft	22.62	1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	TEST @ ↑ Alt.
		P _a	22.14	0.50	0.73	1.1	1.44	2.10	S
Sp2		696.7	22.48	179	232	790	1481	3820	D
		T _a	22.54	136	132	132	132	204	B
		286.9	22.47	2345	2362	2382	2394	2425	R
				964	963.9	964	964.1	964	P
11:02:55	11:03:26	1000ft		0.5	0.72	1.1	1.42	2.05	S Run 1
		P _a	24.01	161	266	413	653	691	D
Sp2		979.4	23.1	153	153	144	145	150	B
		T _a	23.7	2377	2363	2347	2338	2831	R
		286.5	23.42	1003.4	1003.4	1003.3	1003.4	1003.4	P
			23.51						
				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
11:11:13	11:11:46	1000ft	23.6	0.5	0.72	1.1			S Run 2
		P _a	23.08	120	202	361			D
Sp3		979.2	23.0	146	146	147			B aborted due to
		T _a		2327	2332	2356			R end of run
		286.9		1003.4	1003.4	1003.6			P
11:21:55	11:22:25	5000ft	22.9	0.5	0.72	1.08			S Run 2.
		P _a	22.97	105	167	322			D above cloud
Sp4		843.6	23.6	154	154	159			B Changed altitude
		T _a		2465	2478	2479			R @ 315 (end)
		283.0		1006.5	1000.6	1000.6			P
				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
11:46:50	11:47:20	500ft	24.2	0.48	0.7	1.06	1.37	2.05	S Run 7.1
		P _a	25.4	163	215	368	435	732	D
Sp5		1000.3	25.23	225	208	184	175	166	B
		T _a	25.36	2469	2385	2369	2360	2344	R
		287.8	24.84	1006.5	1006.5	1006.5	1006.6	1006.6	P
11:57:20	11:57:46	500ft	25.06	0.49	0.7	1.06	1.37	2.01	S Run 7.1
		P _a	24.88	142	162	331	433	587	D
Sp6		948.5	24.7	160	157	152	151	154	B
		T _a	25.08	2347	2377	2386	2400	2411	R
		287.8	25.21	1006.5	1006.5	1006.6	1006.1	1006.5	P
				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
12:06:30	12:06:58	500ft	24.85	0.48	0.71	1.05	1.37	1.99	S Run 7.1
		P _a	25.62	111	166	277	361	768	D
Sp7		949.5	25.1	151	159	2473.5	170	169	B
		T _a	25.01	2424	2453	164 ↓	2488	2496	R
		288.1	25.3	1006.6	1006.6	1006.5	1006.4	1007.0	P
12:17:50	12:18:18	500ft	24.08	0.48	0.7	1.05	1.59	2.89	S Run 7.1
		P _a	25.6	123	126	118	141	115	D
Sp6		1000.1	24.97	176	177	165	158	164	B
		T _a	25.42	2498	2497	2497	2480	2471	R
		287.9	24.96	1007.3	1007.3	1007.4	1007.4	1007.4	P

B134

CCN LOG

ALLEVIATOR GMT	OFF	HEIGHT	TEMP INLET	STATIC					REMARKS
				1	2	3	4	5	
1:41:30	1:41:55	500ft		1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
		Pa	25.19	0.48	0.69	1.04	1.36	1.97	S
		986.8	25.24	1157	1600	2471	2860	4092	D
		Ta	25.44	211	221	217	253	350	B
		286.0	25.49	2335	320	2317	2315	2317	R
			25.56	995.6	994.3	994.3	994.3	994.4	P
1:49:17	1:49:43	500ft	25.11	0.48	0.69	1.04			S
986.8 Pa	286.2 Ta		25.56	682	1210				D
			25.53	179	183				B
				2356	2323	2315			R
				993.5	992.4	992.4			P
				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
2:20:50	2:21:18	500ft	24.8	0.47	0.68	1.03	1.3	1.94	S
989.2 Pa			25.45	920	1323	2085	3243	3514	D
286.6 Ta			25.61	180	202	206	222	316	B
			25.52	2472	2474	2478	2481	2477	R
			25.4	995.9	995.8	996.3	996.5	996.4	P
2:27:30	2:27:52		25.03	0.47	0.68	1.03	1.33	1.96	S
991.9 Pa			25.6	1408	1832	3054	2932	3300	D
286.3 Ta			25.7	190	194	194	210	272	B
			25.7	2469	2462	2454	2447	2438	R
			25.5	996.8	996.6	997.4	997.3	997.4	P
				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
2:34:27	2:34:51		25.32	0.47	0.68	1.02	1.32	1.95	S
993.5 Pa			26.11	1376	1854	2973	3544	4092	D
286.6 Pa			25.9	174	185	190	190	375	B
			26.26	2427	2419	2410	2387	2364	R
			26.15	999.2	999.0	999.1	999.0	1000	P
				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
									S
									D
									B
									R
									P
									S
									D
									B
									R
									P

Run ended

Filter Sampling Log

Flight No:

B134

Date:

26/09/2005

Operator:

Type of filters mounted in	Top inlet TEFLON/NYLON/PAPER	Bottom inlet TEFLON/PAPER
-----------------------------------	-------------------------------------	----------------------------------

Run No	Disk No 1	Disk No 2	Disk No 3	Top/ Bottom	Time On	Time Off	Flight Run	Accum Vol [l]	Comments
	TOP	MIDDLE	BOTTOM						
Transit	120	89	13	Top	103230	105540		235	Back Ground
Transit	93	111	154	Bottom	103230	105540		490	Back Ground
Filters run1	132	128	16	Top	110225	111845		349	
Filters run1	50	174	83	Bottom	110225	111845		859	
Filters run2	116	54	21	Top	114925	122722		645	
Filters run2	156	117	143	Bottom	114925	122722		1527	
Filters run3	155	144	23	Top	123148	130705		663	
Filters run3	123	140	134	Bottom	122722	130705		1302	
Filters run4	159	52	5	Top	131109	135530		757	
Filters run4	78	108	126	Bottom	131109	135530		1694	
Filters run5	121	114	18	Top	142042	144345		440	
Filters run5	136	101	94	Bottom	142042	144345		781	
Filters run6	146	51	58	Top	145031	150024		0	
Filters run6	96	130	92	Bottom	145031	150024		0	
				Top					
				Bottom					
				Top					
				Bottom					
				Top					
				Bottom					
				Top					
				Bottom					

Flight No. R134

Route SW ENGLAND → KENT → NE ENGLAND

Date 26/9/2005

Take Off 10:00 AM

Bag Samplers: A. McDONALD, D. FAMILIARI

Sheet No. 1

Bag Number	Time on (GMT)	Time off (GMT)	Lat	Lon	Comments
OLD 281	10:30:00	10:30:30	52.3	0.7 W	10,000ft - transit to Bristol Channel
OLD 37	33:00	33:30			"
OLD 10133	36:00	36:30			"
OLD 160	39:00	39:40			"
OLD 97	42:00	42:30	51.9	1.9 W	"
OLD 83	45:00	45:30			"
OLD 112	48:00	48:30			"
OLD 61	51:00	51:30			"
OLD 829	54:00	54:30			"
" 298	57:00	57:30			
" 271	11:02:00	11:02:30			~1000ft Run 1 Run 1 start
" 256	03:00	03:30			2x1000ft.
" 247	04:00	04:30			
" 235	05:00	05:30			
" 834	06:00	06:30			
" 269	07:10	07:40			
" 503	08:10	08:40			
" 284	09:10	09:40			
" 115	11:00	11:35			
" 1304	12:00	12:30			
" 111	13:00	13:30			
" 43	14:00	14:30			
" 1014	15:00	15:30			
" 198	16:00	16:30			
" 2007	17:00	17:30			
" 9	18:00	18:30			End of Run 1
" 52	19:18	19:48			
" 24	20:15	20:45			
" 550	21:20	21:50			Run 2 (5,000ft)
" 1202	22:10	22:40			
" 162	23:00	23:30			
" 73	24:00	24:30			
" 54	25:00	25:30			
" 81	26:00	26:30			
" 143	27:00	27:30			
" 62	28:00	28:30			Run 3 (6,000ft)
" 8	29:00	29:30			
05-624	31:30	32:00			Descent 6,000ft → 2,000ft
OLD-174	33:00	33:30			2,000ft.
05-238	34:00	34:30			
05-492	35:00	35:30			

Bristol Channel

Run 1 start

2,000ft

Flight No. B134

Route

Date 26/9/2005

Take Off 10 GMT

Bag Samplers: A. McDONALD, D. FAYOLAR

Sheet No. 2

Bag Number	Time on (GMT)	Time off (GMT)	Lat	Lon	Comments
05-281	11:36:20	11:36:50	50	3.14	
05-629	37:30	38:00			
05-118	39:00	39:30			Descent
05-117	43:30	44:00			500ft
05-284	45:00	45:30			250ft
05-302	47:00	47:30			500ft - Start of Run
" 159	48:00	48:30			
" 350	49:00	49:30			
" 352	50:00	50:30	50.0	1.9	
" 153	51:00	51:30			
" 377	52:00	52:30			
" 604	53:00	53:30			
" 111	54:00	54:30			
" 550	55:00	55:30			
" 137	56:00	56:30			
" 438	57:00	57:30			
" 114	58:00	58:30			
" 034	59:00	59:30			
086	12:00:00	12:00:30			
" 138	01:00	01:30			
" 395	02:00	02:30			Point 44
" 175	03:00	03:30			
" 369	04:00	04:30			
" 183	05:00	05:30			
" 620	06:00	06:30			
" 120	07:00	07:30			
" 065	08:00	09:30			
" 623	09:00	09:30			
" 054	10:00	10:30			
" 606	11:00	11:30			
" 108	12:00	17:30	50.6	0.0	
" 614	13:00 13:00	13:30			
" 045	14:00	14:30			
" 113	15:03 15:00	15:33			
319	16:00	16:30			Point 43
627	17:00	17:30			
" 516	18:00	18:30			
" 135	19:00	19:30			
116	20:00	20:30			
156	21:00	21:30			
044	22:00	22:30			

Flight No. B134Route Date 26/9/2005Take Off 10 GMTBag Samplers: A. McDONALD, D. FANULARISheet No. 3

Bag Number	Time on (GMT)	Time off (GMT)	Lat	Lon	Comments
05-278	12:23:00	12:23:30	50.9	1.1E	
" 628	24:00	24:30			
" 105	25:00	25:30			
" 072	26:00	26:30			Point 42
" 015	27:00	27:30			
" 181	28:00	28:30			
" 608	29:00	29:30			
" 019	30:00	30:30			
" 041	31:00	31:30			
" 370	32:00	32:30			
308	33:00	33:30			
253	34:00	34:30			
558	35:00	35:30			
151	36:00	36:30			
059	37:00	37:00			
353	38:00	38:30			
037	39:00	39:30			
609	40:00	40:30			
315	41:00	41:30	52.0	1.8E	
293	42:00	42:30			
439	43:00	43:30			
154	44:00	44:30			
401	45:00	45:30			
555	46:00	46:30			
021	47:00	47:30			
139	48:00	48:30			
" 070	49:00	49:30			
244	50:00	50:30	52.5	1.8E	
" 494	51:00	51:30			
090	52:00	52:30			
155	53:00	53:30			
605	54:00	54:30			
552 552	55:00	55:30			
344	56:00	56:30			
067	57:00	57:30			
6616	58:00	58:30			
603	59:00	59:30			
272	13:00:00	13:00:30			
477	13:01:00	01:30	53	1.0E	
269	02:00	02:30			
317	03:00	03:30			

Flight No. B134Route Date 26/9/2005Take Off 10 GMTBag Samplers: A. McDONALD D. FATOLARISheet No. 4

Bag Number	Time on (GMT)	Time off (GMT)	Lat	Lon	Comments
05-023	13:04:00	04:30			
259	05:00	05:30			
027	06:00	06:30			
520	07:00	07:40			
453	08:00	08:30			
109	08:00 09:00	09:30			
129	10:00	10:30			
430	13:11:00	11:30			
049	12:00	12:30			
176	13:00	13:30			
241	14:00	14:30			
376	15:00	15:30			
373	16:00	16:30			
541	17:00	17:30			
514	18:00	18:30			
378	19:00	19:30			
227	20:00	20:30			
375	21:00	21:30			
298	22:00	22:30	54.2	0.1W	
326	23:00	23:30			
166	24:00	24:30			
039	25:00	25:30			
539	26:00	26:30			
234	27:00	27:30			
208	28:00	28:30			
146	29:00	29:30			
545	30:00	30:30			
461	31:00	31:30			
444	32:00	32:30			
542	33:00	33:30			
548	34:00	34:30			
225	35:00	35:30			
501	36:00	36:30			
502	37:00	37:30			
05-472	38:00	38:30			
020158	39:00	39:30	55	1.2W	
" 543	40:00	40:30			
05-540	41:00	41:30			
" 613	42:00	42:30			
" 491	43:00	43:30			
05-500	44:00	44:30			

Flight No. B134

Route

Date 26/9/2005

Take Off 10 GMT

Bag Samplers: A. McDONALD D. FANULARI

Sheet No. 5

Bag Number	Time on (GMT)	Time off (GMT)	Lat	Lon	Comments
05-529	13:45:00	13:45:30	55.4	1.Sd.	
05-305	46:00	46:30			
"-365	47:00	47:30			
560	48:00	48:30			
504	49:00	49:30			
232	50:00	50:30			
490	51:00	51:30			
309	52:02	52:32			
536	53:00	53:30			
722	54:00	54:30			
2360	55:00	55:30			End of Run
412	58:00	58:30			250 ft
270	59:00	59:30			Climb to 1000 ft
467	14:00:50	01:20			1000 ft
306	14:04:16	04:40			2000 ft
422	14:14:00	14:30			6000 ft
204	22:00	22:30			500 ft - start of run
200 ft	21:00	21:30			500 ft - start of run
372	22:00	22:30			
103	23:00	23:30			
527	24:00	24:30			
482	25:00	25:30			
275	26:00	26:30			
276	27:00	27:30			
380	28:00	28:30			
231	29:00	29:30			
536	30:00	30:30			
480	31:00	31:30			
466	32:00	32:30			
277	33:00	33:30			
537	34:00	34:30	54.2	0-0E	
497	35:00	35:30			
274	36:00	36:30			
413	37:00	37:30			
257	38:00	38:30			
405	39:00	39:30			
193	40:00	40:30			
289	41:00	41:30			
229	42:00	42:30			
240	42:00	43:30			End of Run
200	48:00	48:30			
437	51:30	52:00			↓ 10,000 ft
445	53:00	53:30			

Turn South

WAS & PAN Sampling Summary

TIME	BOTTLE #	COMMENTS	FINAL PRESSURE (bar)
		Cases 1, 2, 4, 5 and 7 available	
		Argon Cylinder = 140 bar	
		WAS cylinder = 50 bar	
		Time Check at 9:34:50	
		using Fast Fill 30s fill time.	
11:02:25		Run 1.1 at 1000ft	
11:07:44	1	Clean background air > Bristol channel	3.36
11:14:10	2	clean background air, 2 miles from waypoint 37	3.33
11:15:50		turning at 37	
11:18:32		end of Run 1.1 at 1000ft, waypoint 48	
		ascending to FL 50.	
11:21:12		Start of Run 2 at 5000ft	
11:24:22	3	5000ft	3.19
11:26:42		end of Run 2	
11:27:59		Start of Run 3 at 6000ft	
11:29:05		end of Run 3	
11:29:25		Start of Profile 1	
11:33:00		end of Profile 1 Start of Run 4 at 2000ft	
11:38:05	4	2000ft	3.30
11:34:44		end of Run 4	
		point 46	
11:38:06		Start of profile 2 descending from 5000ft to 500ft.	

WAS & PAN Sampling Summary

TIME	BOTTLE #	COMMENTS	FINAL PRESSURE (bar)
11:43:22		end of profile 2 start of Run 5	
11:43:54	5	500 ft	3.25
		5 m to waypoint 45	
11:44:34		end of run 5 reference	
11:45:01		end of profile 2 start of 250 ft run 6	
11:45:04	6	250 ft	3.36
11:46:01		end of Run 6	
11:46:43		start of Run 7.1 at 500ft	
11:48:42		waypoint 45	
11:50:42	7	500 ft	3.35
12:01		waypoint 44	
12:02:12	8	500ft	3.34
12:10:09	9	near Brighton	3.35
12:16:10	10	NOx ↑	3.36
12:16:45		waypoint 43	
12:27:40		Waypoint 42	
12:28:28	11	NOx ↑ CO ↑	3.36
12:39:45		waypoint 41	
12:40:10	12	NO2 ↑	3.35

WAS & PAN Sampling Summary

TIME	BOTTLE #	COMMENTS	FINAL PRESSURE (bar)
12:43:02	13		3.35
12:51:52		going round Norfolk coast - cutting corner before point 40	
13:01:45	14	London plume?	3.35
13:07:18	15		3.35
		Case 5 not flushing properly going to case 4 instead Case 4 flushing at N 1.42	
13:10:21	33		3.34
		Software still thinks its flushing case 5 → reloading it.	
13:15:25	34		3.35
13:18:49	35	Doncaster / Grimsby? plume	3.35
13:21:30	36	Plume	3.35
~ 13:24		FL 12?	
13:30		~ halfway between 80 and 79	
13:31:06	37	highest aerosol - Teeside plume?	3.35
13:29		79	
13:38:58	38	plume - Teeside plume?	3.35
13:42		78	

WAS & PAN Sampling Summary

TIME	BOTTLE #	COMMENTS	FINAL PRESSURE (bar)
13:43:44	39	very large MAX spike cement works just upwind	3.35
13:51:11	40	Phone - pass Newcastle.	3.34
		Case 2 Flushing at N 1.15	
13:52		St Abbs	
13:55:22		end of Run 7.1	
13:57:48		Run 8 250 ft	
13:57:58	49	250 ft	3.34
13:56:48		end of Run 8 profile ascent to 1000 ft - profile 3	
14:00:43		Run 9 at 1000 ft	
14:00:48	50	1000 ft	3.34
14:01:43		end of 9 recommencing profile 3 77 turns 79	
14:04:04	51	Run 10 at 2000 ft	
14:04:04	51	2000 ft	3.29
14:05:04		end of Run 10 ascending to 6000 ft	
14:04:32		Run 11 Run 11	
14:09:56	52	at 6000 ft	3.12
		used 27 bottles so far. 4 - 12 left.	
14:17:29		end of Run 11	

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B** 134

Date: 26th September 2005

Instrument	Fitted	Operated	Instrument	Fitted	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>			<u>Cloud Physics</u>		
INU		Y	Probes		
XR5M GPS		Y	FFSSP		Y
Cruciform GPS		N	PCASP		Y
Satcom C		Y	2D-P		Y
Satcom H		Y	2D-C		Y
<u>Thermometers</u>			Cloudscope		N
De-Iced Temp		Y	SID 1		N
Non De-Iced		Y	SID 2		N
Heimann		N	HVPS		N
<u>Hygrometers</u>			CIP25		N
G. Eastern		Y	CIP100		N
J. Williams		Y			
Nevzorov		Y			
TWC		N			
FWVS		N	Racks:		
<u>Radiometers</u>			INC		N
Upper Clear	Y	N	CCN / CNC		Y
“ Red	Y	N	CVI		N
“ Silicon	Y	N			
“ JO1D	Y	N	<u>Aerosol</u>		
Lower Clear	Y	N	PSAP		N
“ Red	Y	N	Nephelometer		N
“ Silicon	Y	N	Filters		Y
“ JO1D	Y	N	AMS		Y
<u>Large Radiometers</u>					
TAFTS		N			
MARSS		N			
DEIMOS		N	<u>Others:</u>		
ARIES		N	NIR TDLAS		N
SWS		N	2BT O3		N
<u>Chemistry</u>			VACC		N
Ozone		Y	PEROXIDE		N
SO2		Y	Formaldehyde		N
NOX		Y	ADA		N
CO		Y	CPI		N
ORAC		N	NOxy		Y
PAN		N	PTRMS		Y
PERCA		N	Bag Sampling		Y
WAS		Y	Tube Sampling		N

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B134

Date: 26th September 2005

Instruments

1. TWC not fitted
2. Upper and Lower BBRs DLUs not fitted
3. Butanol spill pre-flight beside AMS rack. Cleaned up with tissues.
4. SID 1 pc – dropped out around power transfer, then okay.
5. Camera pictures – lost RFC, DFC & UFC during take-off roll. Reset Video Titler and camera power then okay.
6. FFC window – splodge collected in-flight.
7. DFC picture – colours very washed out in-flight.

Aircraft

1. Airstairs u/s (hydraulic leak).
2. Start-up delayed due to restriction of fire cover this afternoon (i.e. not available until after 1600).
3. Headset faulty at Core Console Aft – handed over to CCM

Satcom H Calls nil

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following logs are not available for flight B134:

Log	Reason
De-brief	Sortie De-brief yet to be created by Eiko Nemitz
NOxy	No log is ever taken for NOxy
PTrMS	No log is ever taken for PTrMS
AMS	Log only of interest to instrument operator so no copy left with FAAM

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with FAAM (at 31 Oct 2005) :

- 3 x Forward Facing Cameras
- 3 x Downward Facing Cameras